

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

REAL-TIME RISK ASSESSMENT IN FOREX TRADING

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the issue of real-time risk assessment, which is one of the biggest problems in the financial sector. In particular, it covers risk models implemented within the framework of infinite technology capabilities (INFINITECH) and their integration with relevant technological tools to ensure the processing of large volumes of input data. The presented Infinittech application, in addition to using a number of well-known risk models, also introduces a new model based on deep learning techniques. These assessments can be updated in almost real-time using streaming financial data and can be used to conduct "what if" analysis for portfolio changes.

The Infinittech solution can become a valuable tool for professionals involved in high-frequency trading - an area where consistent risk assessment in real time is required. It should be noted that the existing architecture can also be used with different risk models optimized for different financial portfolios. In addition, additional functions can be integrated into the system in the form of microservices, in accordance with the Infinittech reference architecture.

Keywords: portfolio risk, risk assessments, risk models, Value at Risk, Variance-Covariance approach.

1. Introduction

Risk assessment is required to determine the probability and magnitude of a loss on a loan or investment. Sometimes, incorrect models or incorrect assumptions can lead to large capital losses. Therefore, risk assessment and continuous monitoring are of great importance in investment banking. This was also observed in a number of financial institutions during the 2008 financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic. Despite the digitalization of the financial sector, many companies are far from accurate, real-time risk assessment capabilities. This is due to the fact that portfolio risk assessments are currently updated only once a day, usually in batches at night. This is not sufficient for trading in higher frequency markets such as Forex [1,2]. Surprisingly, this issue still remains an open problem for many banks and asset management companies. In these organizations, risk assessment is often outsourced to third-party consulting companies responsible for risk monitoring and regulatory compliance, and this process is carried out in accordance with a pre-agreed investment strategy. In addition, even in some cases, even if a real-time overview of trading positions is provided, the data necessary to calculate risk measures and other important indicators is updated only once a day. As a result, the level of risk arising from price changes occurring throughout the day is not properly monitored, which can lead to inefficiency in both trading and investment.

The main obstacle to real-time risk monitoring in high-frequency trading, depending on the complexity of the algorithms, is the speed of calculating financial risks. Usually, there is a certain balance between speed and accuracy in calculating financial risks. Although risk models that require fewer computational resources can provide immediate results, they are not considered

sufficiently reliable in the financial sector. In addition, real-time risk monitoring is a requirement of administrative bodies. This requirement can only be met if risk information is updated in a timely manner.

[2,3], the need for risk assessment in trading, investment and other financial processes is highlighted. This is because poor risk monitoring can lead to ineffective investments, capital losses and fines from regulatory authorities. Robust risk models that can provide real-time results are valuable assets for investment banking. This paper presents a financial tool that can provide real-time and pre-trade risk assessment of FX portfolios. Financial risk is measured in terms of both value at risk and expected shortfall. The proposed application, based on state-of-the-art data management technologies, provides real-time risk assessments using the latest market data [4]. These features, together with the pre-trade analysis provided, make this solution a valuable tool for professionals in high-frequency trading and investment banking in general.

This paper presents a new tool called Artificial Intelligence-Risk-Assessment. This tool is presented as one of the potentially important solutions in the FX market. More precisely, this tool is aimed at solving the problem of real-time risk assessment in the Forex market. The main advantages offered by this tool are divided into three main areas: risk models real-time management; pre-trade analysis. The basic architecture of the system is presented, which ensures the smooth operation of these components with each other. The proposed tool is based on a containerized microservice architecture. The system consists of various components, and these components communicate with each other asynchronously. As a result, a real-time data processing pipeline (container) is formed. This model is depicted in Figure 1 [6].

Figure 1. Data processing line [7]

2. Portfolio Risk

Portfolio risk is the probability that the set of assets that make up the portfolio will not achieve its financial goals. A portfolio is an investor's "basket" of financial instruments, and Portfolio risk is the risk arising from the price volatility and probability of loss of the assets in that "basket". Each capital in the portfolio carries its own risk. Thus, the higher the potential return, the greater the risk. In order to measure this risk quantitatively, the future indicators of each asset, i.e. its returns, must be predicted. For this purpose, various models and theories have been put forward regarding the nature of financial time series. Most of these models assume that the returns of the underlying assets follow a certain distribution, for example, a Gaussian distribution. They attempt to determine its parameters, the average price and variance of the asset's returns, based on past indicators. In addition, portfolio risk also depends on the weighted combination of component assets and their mutual correlation. Thus, according to Modern Portfolio Theory, which is based on the Normal distribution for financial returns, the risk indicator of a portfolio under a known probability distribution can be determined through the distribution parameters (1) [2,3]:

$$\mu_p = E(R_p) = \sum_i w_i E(R_i), i = \overline{1, n} \quad (1)$$

where R_p is the portfolio return, R_i is the return of the i th asset, and w_i is the weight of that asset in the portfolio,

$$\sigma_p^2 = \sum_i w_i^2 \sigma_i^2 + \sum_i \sum_{i \neq j} w_i w_j \sigma_i \sigma_j \rho_{ij}, i, j = \overline{1, n} \quad (2)$$

where, σ is the sample standard deviation of the periodic returns of the asset, and ρ_{ij} is the correlation coefficient between the returns of assets i, j .

Furthermore, the Efficient Market Hypothesis suggests that in highly efficient markets, such as the foreign exchange market, the value of a financial instrument reflects all available information about that instrument. Therefore, the risk models used must be constantly updated with the latest market data to provide reliable portfolio risk assessments. There is a particular need for continuous updating of risk assessments in high-frequency market transactions. In this area, traders mainly manage multiple portfolios based on algorithmic trading, combining different strategies — in terms of holding period, composition, risk profile and volume — [1-5,7]. Therefore, a special tool is needed that can process large volumes of market and trade data and pro-

vide risk assessments. These assessments must be updated in near real-time to reflect intraday volatility, which can lead to liquidity and capital losses.

3. Risk Models

The proposed application uses two main risk measurement methods that are widely used not only in risk management, but also in financial management, financial reporting and capital calculation by financial management institutions: value at risk and expected loss.

The first risk measurement method, Value at Risk (VOR), measures the maximum amount of loss that an investment can suffer over a certain period of time (usually one day) and within a certain probability of reliability. There are three main approaches to calculating VOR: parametric, non-parametric and semi-parametric [5,6,8]. The "Artificial Intelligence – Risk – Assessment" tool presents four VOR models based on these approaches in order to improve the risk monitoring process [9].

Parametric. The most widely used parametric VOR method is based on the Variance-Covariance (VC) approach. According to the main assumption of this method, portfolio returns are normally distributed and the dispersion of market data is assumed to be known [10]. In addition, a suitable "history" window should be defined and the variance-covariance matrix of returns should be calculated [11,12,13]. The VOR is calculated by formula (3):

$$V_a R^\alpha = Z_{1-\alpha} \sqrt{w^T \Sigma w}, \quad (3)$$

where, z , α , w and Σ are the standard price, the probability of the VOR forecast, the weights of the portfolio assets and the covariance matrix of the portfolio assets, respectively.

Non-parametric. Among the non-parametric approaches, the well-known Historical Simulation (HS) method was chosen [14,15]. In this method, the past returns of the portfolio over a certain time window and the chosen confidence level are taken into account when calculating the VOR. As a first step, the historical portfolio returns are sorted from small to large, then the worst n -day indicator corresponding to the required confidence probability is taken as the VOR. For example, when calculating the daily 95% VOR based on 100 days of data, the best result among the returns falling in the worst 5% corresponds to the 95% VOR. Thus, TS

is a computationally efficient model that gives satisfactory results when using large historical windows. However, in this case, the VOR values are taken high, which limits the acceptable investment strategies.

Semi-parametric. Within the framework of the semi-parametric approach, a Monte Carlo (MC) model has been developed [10-14]. In this method, the mean and standard deviation of returns are calculated based on available historical data, and then random MC samples from a Gaussian distribution are generated using these values. To calculate RD, the distribution of portfolio returns over the future period is modeled (4):

$$V_{\alpha}R^{\alpha} = q_{1-\alpha}, \quad (4)$$

where q_{α} is the α^{th} percentile of the continuous compound return (e.g. $\alpha = 0.05$ for a 5% risk).

Semi-parametric with RNNs. In addition, the tool introduces a novel semi-parametric VOR model that combines deep neural networks with ML simulations [11,13,15]. In this approach, the parameters of the return distribution are first estimated using a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)-based model, and the network output is used to predict all possible future returns using the ML method. The VOR is then calculated using formula (4) above. This RNN model, called DeepAR, is provided by the GluonTS Python library for deep learning-based time series modeling. The model is able to capture nonlinear dependencies of the input time series, including features such as seasonality, which allows for more accurate quantile estimates. Moreover, DeepAR can accept multiple time series at the same time, which enables joint cross-learning from their historical behavior [16]. As a result, dynamic changes in one time series can affect the forecast distributions of other time series.

Risk assessment can alternatively be performed using the Expected Shortfall (ES) method, also known as Conditional Value at Risk (CVR). This is a conservative risk measure and calculates the loss on the assumption that the portfolio loss is higher than the calculated VOR. ES was initially proposed as a practical and reliable alternative to RD; one of its main advantages is the sub-additivity feature that VOR does not have. For this reason, many financial institutions have adopted it as an internal risk measure. ES can be calculated using the parametric equation (5) [10,15,16]:

$$ES_p^{\alpha} = -\mu_p + \mu_{\sigma} \frac{\phi(\Phi^{-1}(\alpha))}{\alpha}, \quad (5)$$

where, $\phi(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi e}} e^{-\frac{x^2}{2}}$ is the density function, $\Phi(x)$ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, and $\Phi^{-1}(\alpha)$ is the standard normal quantile; μ_p and σ_p denote the mean and standard deviation of the portfolio returns, respectively.

The application's user interface offers a separate page for analyzing and back-testing the risk assessments submitted. This feature allows the user to comparatively evaluate the actual performance of different VOR/ES models at both the 95% and 99% confidence levels.

4. Real-time management

Providing the above-mentioned risk assessments using the latest available data is a very difficult task. The main reason for this is that currency market prices are updated at an unevenly high frequency (e.g., 1-8

seconds). In addition, even small price changes can have a significant impact on the value of portfolios, especially in cases where a high risk/return strategy is applied. Therefore, additional technologies are needed that can combine continuous data management with online analytical processing capabilities.

Within the framework of the Infinitech project, this issue is addressed through a new data management platform called InfiniSTORE. InfiniSTORE extends the existing advanced database platform and introduces two important innovations that enable real-time analytical processing of transactional data.

1. The platform's hybrid transaction and analytical processing engine allows for very high data ingest speed and simultaneous analytical operations on that data. This eliminates the need to transfer historical data to a temporary storage that is slow and inherently batch-oriented.

2. The online aggregation function ensures efficient execution of aggregate operations, which significantly reduces the response time to queries by several times.

The implementation of the AI-Risk-Assessment model requires the data warehouse to perform two main functions: first, to store raw input ticker data and risk assessments, and second, to provide online data aggregation and integrated query processing on both the data being processed and the stored data. These requirements are met by InfiniSTORE and the underlying LeanXcale database through a dual interface. This interface allows for the reception of operational data at any speed and at the same time parallel processing of analytical queries on live data.

To achieve the main goal of the application, which is to measure risk in a timely manner throughout the day — for example, to update the RD/GC approximately every 15 minutes — the ticker data that enters must be resampled 1-8 times per second at the required frequency. LeanXcale provides an online aggregation capability that enables declarative real-time data analysis with standard SQL statements. This mechanism allows you to specify only the required aggregate operations—for example, the average price per quarter hour for each currency pair—and the result is automatically calculated in advance. This turns what would normally take a long time to perform into lightweight operations that require only a single value, eliminating the need to scan the entire data set.

5. CONCLUSION

The portfolio risk assessment in the paper has a two-stage procedure.

In the first stage, both VOR and ES are calculated as separate univariate time series for each portfolio instrument based on the latest market prices obtained from the real-time management tools described in Section 4. It should be noted that these calculations are performed in the background and are automatically updated as new data becomes available.

The second stage is related to user input. For example, when the user experiments with new trading positions, the weight of each asset is determined and the VOR/ES indicators of the portfolio are calculated based on the univariate risk assessments. This procedure is

completed in a very short time, as it only requires simple matrix algebra.

References

1. Andersen, T. G., Bollerslev, T., Diebold, F. X., & Vega, C. (2007). *Journal of International Economics*, 73(2), 251. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2007.02.004>
2. George Fatouros and et all. *Addressing Risk Assessments in Real-Time for Forex Trading*. 2021, pp. 159-179. DOI:10.1007/978-3-030-94590-99
3. Mingle, D. L., Humphrey, D. B., & Summers, B. J. (1987). *Economic Review* 73. https://www.richmondfed.org/-/media/richmondfedorg/publications/research/economic_review
4. Bredin, D., & Hyde, S. (2004). *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 31(9–10), 1389.
5. <https://www.geeksforgoeks.org/software-engineering/overview-of-data-pipeline/>
6. Kearns, M., & Nevmyvaka, Y. (2013). High frequency trading: New realities for traders, markets, and regulators.
7. Préfontaine, J., Desrochers, J., & Godbout, L. (2010). The Analysis of comments received by the BIS on principles for sound liquidity risk management and supervision. *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 9(7). <https://doi.org/10.19030/iber.v9i7.598>
8. Nguyen, J. (2004). The efficient market hypothesis: Is it applicable to the foreign exchange market? Department of Economics, University of Wollongong. <https://ro.uow.edu.au/commwkpapers/104>
9. Fama, E. F. (2021). *Efficient capital markets II*. University of Chicago Press.
10. Gomber, P., & Haferkorn, M. (2015). *Encyclopedia of information science and technology* (3rd ed., pp. 1–9). IGI Global.
11. Markowitz, H. (1955). The optimization of a quadratic function subject to linear constraints. Technical Report. RAND CORP SANTA MONICA CA.
12. Longerstaey, J., & Spencer, M. (1996). *Morgan Guaranty Trust Company of New York*, 51, 54.
13. Chang, Y. P., Hung, M. C., & Wu, Y. F. (2003). *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 32(4), 1041.
14. Hong, L. J., Hu, Z., & Liu, G. (2014). *ACM Transactions on Modeling and Computer Simulation (TOMACS)*, 24(4), 1.
15. Dinh-Tuan, H., Beierle, F., & Garzon, S. R. (2019). 2019 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Cyber Physical Systems (ICPS) (pp. 23–30). IEEE.
16. Kreps, J., Narkhede, N., & Rao, J. (2011). *Kafka: A distributed messaging system for log processing*. In *Proceedings of the NetDB* (Vol. 11).